

РОЛЬ АУТЕНТИЧНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ КАК УЧЕБНОГО ЭЛЕМЕНТА В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АКТИВНОЙ ЛЕКСИКЕ СТУДЕНТОВ-ЛИНГВИСТОВ

THE ROLE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AS AN EDUCATIONAL ELEMENT IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ACTIVE VOCABULARY TO LINGUIST STUDENTS

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В статье рассматривается методический потенциал аутентичных материалов в процессе обучения студентов-лингвистов активному тематическому вокабуляру. Приводится характеристика таких понятий, как «аутентичность» и «активный тематический вокабуляр», а также анализируются методические особенности каждой из используемых дефиниций. Автор делает акцент на том, что использование аутентичных материалов, как в форме видеоряда, так и письменных, повышает мотивацию студентов, обучающихся по направлению подготовки 45.03.02 «Лингвистика», к изучению иностранного языка, что положительно влияет на формирование социокультурной компетенции в целом, в значительной степени повышающих качество как устной, так и письменной речи.

The article examines the methodological potential of authentic materials in the process of teaching linguists students an active thematic vocabulary. The characteristic of such concepts as "authenticity" and "active thematic vocabulary" is given, as well as the methodological features of each of the definitions used are analyzed. The author emphasizes that the use of authentic materials, both in the form of a video series and written, increases the motivation of students studying in the direction of training 45.03.02 "Linguistics" to study a foreign language, which positively affects the formation of socio-cultural competence in general, significantly improving the quality of both oral and written speech.

Ключевые слова: *аутентичные материалы, активный вокабуляр, активная лексика, студенты-лингвисты, параметры аутентичного текста, социокультурный контекст.*

Key words: *authentic materials, active vocabulary, active lexicon, linguistic students, authentic text parameters, sociocultural context.*

R*levance.* The language teaching situation aimed at increasing the students' professional competence is not successful enough without the attempt to approach the speech the native speaker's one. That's why there should be all the possible ways worked out for finding a proper solution. Being fully relied on the teaching experience it should be mentioned that authentic materials must be considered as a possible remedy to make the students speak accurately and fluently. It will be easier, faster and more effective to improve students' productive skills if they are based

on authentic materials. As reaching proficient levels is a universal goal for the contemporary linguist in the high school, this objective becomes of an especially challenge for English language students particularly in the domain of productive speech. Speaking and writing has been identified as one of the most essential skills because the world has become so text-oriented. Due to this change of effective techniques to improve those skills is in great demand.

Problem possessing. The level of mastering the foreign language at various levels of linguistic education is strictly governed by the main document regulating the academic process in general – the Higher Education Federal State Academic Standards.

The Higher Education Federal State Standards put forward certain requirements to both studying and teaching a foreign language as an academic subject that allows a linguistic student to approach to socialisation and adaptation in society including a foreign one as the qualification mentioned above really requires an entire mastering the cross-cultural competence which cannot be obtained without acquiring the thematic active lexical skills.

Materials and methods. A mixed-method research design (qualitative and quantitative research design) was used to find the effectiveness of developing grammar skills in teaching writing, as well as to collect data for the current study as it was used to describe attitudes, beliefs, opinions and other types of information.

Research results. When studying foreign languages, students acquire and develop the necessary social skills and abilities, using a foreign language as a means of cognition, communication and interaction. Based on the progressive teaching techniques and methods, it is necessary to create conditions for the students' socialisation, developing personal qualities and forming a certain level of social skills, which would allow them to develop and bring their abilities to life. At present, it is recommended to develop foreign languages teaching system in an educational Institution, in particular, when making requirements for the foreign language proficiency level, correlate the expected results with foreign language proficiency international scales. According to Professor D. Larsen-Freeman, the University of Michigan English Language Institute, authentic materials are an integral part of language learning [2, p. 43]. In such a way, this fact cannot be left without specific attention in the foreign language teaching and learning process directed at forming the linguistic students' cross-cultural competence which according to our observation is absolutely impossible without learning the topical up-to-date vocabulary that makes our speech similar to the native speakers' one'.

M.V. Lyakhovitsky, the Russian methodologist, believes that the linguistic environment is necessary for any foreign material better assimilation, and everything that is used as an additional academic element can be considered as an auxiliary tool in learning a foreign language. Such auxiliary means as a way of a foreign language environment illusion help at least to motivate positively and involve any student in learning a foreign language [3].

This is fully facilitated by the quality of selected educational material, including the authentic one, with the help of which it is possible to improve knowledge, expand vocabulary and conduct the process of mastering a new vocabulary in the student's speech.

In the article "Authentic Educational Text Parameters" E.V. Nosonovich and R.P. Milrud say that it is more expedient to teach a foreign language based on authentic materials, that is, on materials taken from original sources which are not meant for academic purposes. On the other hand, they point out that such materials are sometimes too complex in terms of language and do not always meet specific tasks and learning conditions, while highlighting methodological or educational-authentic texts separately [4, p. 16].

The initial task in learning a language is its propriety and considerability, but at the present stage of teaching a foreign language, these frameworks are expanding the sphere of their application. It becomes favourable to use not only the teaching materials, which are strictly regulated by the Higher Education Federal State Academic Standards, but also using the other sources is reason-

able. Thus, emphasizing the mentioned above, one should resort to the use of various authentic materials.

Benefits of using authentic material in foreign language teaching are the following:

- authentic materials are informative and stimulating to academic process;
- they can be selected according to the audience's interests, or even the students themselves can participate in the selection process;

- authentic materials reflect the real situation of language use in a cultural context.

The use of authentic materials has a number of advantages that contribute to their practical use which particularly are:

- authentic materials have a positive effect on the student's motivation to learning;
- students can get a sense of academic satisfaction using authentic materials;
- authentic materials provide students with information about what is going on worldwide, and therefore, they have a certain internal educational value;
- authentic materials can be easily and quickly found;
- the use of authentic materials contributes to a more creative approach to learning, etc.

However, in addition to the advantages, there are certain disadvantages while using authentic materials in teaching linguistic students a foreign language:

- authentic materials may be too culturally biased;
- in other words, they may be too difficult to perceive and understand outside the boundaries of the language community;
- active vocabulary does not always meet the students' needs at a particular stage of learning a foreign language;
- special training is needed, which can take lecturers a lot of time while developing academic materials;
- the material can quickly become obsolete, etc. [4, p. 17].

At the present stage, a fairly popular way of teaching a foreign language is referring to authentic video material. Using authentic video materials in teaching a foreign language to linguistic students has become widespread, as it contributes to immersion into the virtual space, which is an authentic virtual interactive language environment. There is a certain classification of authentic video material: feature films, documentaries, animated films, interactive videos (cartoons), TV shows, talk shows, interviews, clips, commercials, movie trailers, etc.

The written authentic materials can be also identified as: books, magazines, newspapers, blogs, and the like.

Since the main requirement of the Higher Education Federal State Academic Standards is the acquiring and development skills and abilities in a foreign language communication, using authentic materials will be necessary due to the fact that authentic materials are an integral part of immersion into the culture of a foreign language.

In order to fully master the active vocabulary extracted from the authentic sources, it becomes really necessary to emphasize on authentic texts no matter what their origin is – either video or the written ones. Thus, the Higher Education Federal State Educational Standards put forward some requirements for teaching reading and speaking skills, which will help to use active vocabulary much more effectively.

In the aspect of the formation reading and speaking students' skills, the Higher Education Federal State Academic Standards make the following requirements concerning the foreign language communicative competence, expansion and systematisation of knowledge about the language, further mastery of the general speech culture for a better understanding of textual sources.

Consequently, reading and speaking increasingly acts as an independent type of speech activity, when the student reads not so much in order to complete the learning task, but in order to obtain

the necessary information from the text and use it. The completeness and accuracy of information extraction depends on the specific language task.

Modern authentic texts can and should be considered as the sources of learning to read and speak at a level close to the native speaker. They contribute to a stronger assimilation of sociocultural information and the use of modern information technologies [1].

Conclusion. Thus, working with authentic texts in teaching a foreign language to linguistic students plays a paramount role. Reading motivation is based on the awareness of its usefulness and necessity for expanding the boundaries of knowledge by mastering a foreign language.

In our opinion, the use of authentic materials in teaching productive skills to linguistic students is appropriate. However, one should not forget about the level of requirements for each year of study or the individual characteristics of students. It is much more effective to use authentic materials in classes with an Intermediate and higher language level which makes it appropriate and should always be used when planning a foreign language session, especially when the lecturer uses authentic materials.

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